

Interview Preparation Document

This document is designed to support your interview preparation at Häme University of Applied Sciences. The questions below will be read by the interviewer prior to your interview and will form a foundation for your interview discussion.

Kindly answer the questions in as much detail as you deem necessary (you may use bullet points if you wish). Kindly send this document to HAMK's contact person.

1. Most important research contributions.

Kindly describe your achieved impact in the form of outputs, deliverables and results achieved in academic and/or applied research projects. You can include examples of positive stakeholder and/or peer feedback or recognition.

2. Inclusion of stakeholders in research projects.

Kindly describe your most important contributions in stakeholder inclusion in academic and/or applied research projects.

3. Research dissemination experience.

Kindly describe your most important contributions in disseminating research information and/projects. Please include the information on the platforms used and why, and how you took into consideration the target audiences altered the style of language used etc.

4. Communication skills.

Kindly describe your most valuable communication skills as a researcher. Kindly describe your experience in communicating with different audiences and in different settings and how you have adapted your communication style accordingly.

5. Leadership and supervision skills in research teams.

Kindly describe your most valuable skills and experience in leadership and supervision. This can include examples outside of research. Kindly explain which leadership and supervision skills are most needed when working in a research group.

6. Teamwork skills in research teams.

Kindly describe your most valuable skills and experience in teamwork. This can include examples outside of research. Kindly describe how you have previously adapted your working style in accordance with different team members, project partners, stakeholders etc. Kindly explain which teamwork skills are most needed when working in a research group.

7. Interdisciplinary and field specialization skills.

Kindly describe how you view and value the role of interdisciplinary and field specialization in research. Kindly describe your most valuable contributions to interdisciplinary research and/or field specialization research. Describe your opinion on the most significant benefits and challenges of interdisciplinary research.

8. Added value to HAMK's research team.

Kindly describe the skills and experience you will bring to HAMK's research team. You can include the different tools, methodologies and frameworks which you have experience using, any other specialization you have obtained, and/or any special recognition you have received from peers.

